

A Comprehensive Review of Advances in Smart Agriculture

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Abstract- We analysed the peer-reviewed literature published between 2021 and 2025 focusing on smart agriculture techniques which integrates advanced technologies such as the Internet of Things (IoT), wireless sensor networks (WSN), machine learning, artificial intelligence (AI), unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs), remote sensing, edge-fog-cloud computing, and renewable energy systems to enhance farming efficiency and sustainability. Recent research shows significant progress in precision irrigation, automated monitoring, and data driven decision support systems that optimize water usage and improve crop yield. This paper presents a comprehensive review of forty research papers focused on smart agriculture techniques, highlighting IoT-based soil moisture monitoring, LoRaWAN enabled long-range communication, machine learning-based disease detection, UAV assisted irrigation planning, and solar powered intelligent water systems. The findings show that integrating smart technologies enables resource optimization, climate resilience, and scalable automation across diverse agricultural scenarios. The study contributes a consolidated view of recent advancements to support the development of sustainable agriculture.

Keywords – IoT, AI/ML, Climate Smart Architecture, Precision Agriculture, UAV, DSS, Edge Computing, Greenhouse.

I. INTRODUCTION

Agriculture plays a critical role in global food security, yet traditional farming methods struggle to meet rising demands due to climate variability, water scarcity, labour shortages, and inefficient resource utilization. As the global population grows, the agricultural sector must transition toward modern, data-driven, and automated systems to ensure sustainable food production. The development of Smart Agriculture, also known as Precision Agriculture, integrates digital technologies such as IoT devices, wireless communication networks, AI/ML algorithms, automation, robotics, remote sensing, and cloud computing to collect real-time data and support informed decision-making.

This paper provides a detailed review of recent advancements in smart agriculture by analyzing forty cutting-edge research studies covering IoT-based monitoring systems, machine learning for crop prediction and disease detection, innovative irrigation control mechanisms, energy-efficient agricultural automation, and human-centered AI approaches. The review aims to consolidate current research trends, evaluate performance outcomes, and highlight opportunities and challenges shaping the future of smart farming.

Recent research has demonstrated strong potential for smart agricultural systems to optimize irrigation scheduling, improve

crop health monitoring, conserve water, enhance productivity, and reduce operational cost and environmental impact. Studies show that smart moisture sensing systems, UAV-based imaging, intelligent irrigation controllers, predictive analytics, and renewable energy-powered infrastructures can transform traditional agricultural practices. The adoption of these technologies contributes directly to resource efficiency and climate-smart farming.

II. METHODS

1. Eligibility criteria

Eligibility criteria were established so that the studies chosen were peer reviewed and were of high quality. Only open access studies published between 2021-2025 were chosen to maintain relevancy. Research papers which presented real world case studies, experimental validations or significant theoretical contributions were chosen. Research papers which didn't mention integration of IoT, AI/ML, Climate Smart Architecture, Precision Agriculture, UAV and their impact were discarded. Additionally research papers which were not in the English language were not chosen.

2. Information sources

Multiple sources like IEEE Xplore, Elsevier ScienceDirect, MDPI and Springer were used to find research papers for this review.

3. Search strategy

A structured keyword search was performed using terms related to the IoT, AI, and smart agriculture. The Boolean search query applied was as follows:

("Internet of Things" OR iot OR "wireless sensor networks" OR wsn OR "smart sensors") AND ("artificial intelligence" OR ai OR "machine learning" OR ml OR "deep learning" OR dl) AND ("agriculture" OR "smart farming" OR "precision agriculture") AND ("sensor-based systems" OR "remote sensing" OR "soil sensors" OR "water sensors" OR "climate monitoring" OR "crop monitoring" OR "precision irrigation" OR "precision fertilization")

III. LITERATURE REVIEW

- Presents a wireless sensor network of low cost sensor nodes for soil moisture that can help farmers optimize the irrigation processes in precision agriculture. Each wireless node is composed of four soil moisture sensors that are able to measure the moisture at different depths.
- Studies the difference between low cost capacitive and low cost resistive soil moisture sensors. They compared two capacitive sensors and two resistive sensors and found out that overall the capacitive sensors performed better than the resistive sensors.
- Proposed a LoRaWAN based smart Decision Support System that acquires the input parameters based on real-time monitoring to optimize the yield by improving per hectare production and decreasing water seepage waste.
- Presents a smart weather data management system evaluated by applying machine learning and deep learning models on data from a meteorological station. The system provides many services such as weather time series forecasts and visualization of meteorological data.
- Made a platform based on IoT and CNN for precision agriculture, to monitor environment and provide early disease detection while automatically controlling the irrigation and fertilization in greenhouses.
- Designed a smart IoT enabled drip irrigation system using ESP32 to automate the irrigation process. The system collects data about soil moisture, temperature, air humidity and water flow. Based on this data it makes decisions whether to water the soil or not.
- Uses Unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV)-based crop monitoring system to support irrigation management decisions for cotton farming in Texas, USA. High temporal and spatial resolution images were acquired using a UAV to gather Canopy Cover (CC) data on a cotton field.
- Uses deep learning to make a irrigation system for Anomaly Detection. To prevent agro-field data leakage, this paper presents a low-cost irrigation system that employs artificial intelligence (AI) techniques to analyze anomalies and problems in water usage.
- Developed a smart irrigation system using EC-IoT edge computing, long range radio (LoRa) communication, 4G and GPS. The work aims to increase automation and decrease dependence on cloud computing. The system collects soil moisture, meteorological data, crop growth stage, and soil characteristics to support irrigation decisions.
- Combines satellite remote sensing with soil moisture sensors to assess water stress and improve irrigation in avocado orchards in Dominican Republic. It uses multispectral imagery from Landsat 8 and 9 satellites to obtain vegetation indices (NDVI and SAVI) and NDWI. This data was used to monitor vegetation health, growth stages and soil water contents.
- Made a smart alert and irrigation system with real time monitoring of soil's condition. This system detects the soil's moisture content and temperature. NodeMCU sends the data to cloud based IoT platform for 24/7 monitoring of the soil's condition. A MQTT communication protocol is used for data transmission. The cloud based IoT platform analyses the collected data and sends alert messages and controls the irrigation system according to pre-set threshold conditions.
- Made an integrated edge-fog-cloud architectural platform which enhances the energy efficiency of smart agriculture systems. The study aims to reduce the energy consumption of cloud computing and its subsequent carbon emissions. This system integrates several sensors to process and analyse the agricultural data in the edge-fog-cloud layers.
- Purpose is to integrate renewable energy into cloud and IoT based smart agriculture. The study has 3 objectives: 1. Smart Water Metering to conserve water table; 2. Integrate renewable energy to reduce reliance on fossil fuels and; 3. Smart irrigation to improve crop quality is a survey which studies the use of IoT in Greenhouse based agriculture. It discusses the components of IoT based greenhouse systems, including farming techniques, system categories, network technologies, protocols, sensors, etc. It also discusses success cases from various countries of IoT greenhouse agriculture goal is to develop robotics and automation technology tools that can help assess watering needs for tree crops.
- The primary focus lies in automating the process of Stem Water Potential (SWP). The work aims to automate the laborious task of physical sampling and specimen analysis made a smart irrigation system that allows selective irrigation of localized dry spots in an agriculture field. The irrigation system uses a UAV equipped with a Thermal Infrared camera and a GPS module to generate georeferenced thermal images that indicate the area and location of the dry spots. Smart sprinklers are deployed on

the field to selectively irrigate the dry spot. It uses ML to generate an irrigation pattern.

- The paper studies the current state, challenges and future direction of human-centered AI in smart farming, a core part of Agriculture 5.0. It highlights advances in human in the loop AI that enhances yields, reduce labour and resource use, and improve supply chains.
- The primary objective of this work is to classify diseases of corn plant leaf using IoT and Deep Learning Multi Models. The experiments conducted generated a 99.23% accuracy in the classification of corn leaf diseases.
- The work explores the opportunities and challenges of IoT based soilless farming. It also highlights its role in sustainable agriculture, urban farming, and food security. It also highlights current trends and research gaps. It supports decision making to address food security challenges and promote sustainable agricultural innovations.
- The study's purpose is to find a way to reduce the amount of water lost during the irrigation process using precision farming and smart irrigation. The study achieved 98.24% and 97.31% in irrigation classification and prediction of the best irrigation time, respectively.
- The paper presents a non contact vision system based on a standard video camera to predict the irrigation requirements for loam soil using a neural network. It relies on analyzing the differences in soil color captured by a video camera at different distances, times and illumination levels obtained from loam soil. This data was used as input to an ANN system to make a decision as to whether to irrigate the soil or not. The results shows that this system is simple and robust making it promising to support precision agriculture.
- The paper presents an IoT and deep learning based system that uses soil moisture, temperature, air temperature and humidity sensors to optimize irrigation with minimal human involvement. Data sent to the cloud is processed through regression, clustering, and classification. Experimental results show superior performance achieving 0.971 accuracy.
- This study develops a solar powered automated irrigation system using soil moisture sensor feedback for real time scheduling. Field tests showed accurate soil moisture detection and efficient water delivery control.
- This study models and optimizes a photovoltaic water pumping system for agrivoltaics smart irrigation in Algeria. Using MPPT and a feed forward neural network to predict pump flow based on power and head, results show higher irradiance increases flow, while greater head reduces it.
- This paper introduces an interpretable AI IoT system that monitors environmental conditions and alerts farmers to take timely actions. Using fuzzy logic it is adaptable to different sensors, crops, soils, and climates. Machine learning detects anomalous data form security or hardware issues.
- The paper presents a method for designing efficient surface irrigation systems based on topographical and geometrical farmland characteristics. Using digital elevation models, slope data, land shape, the method divides fields into plots and designs ditch networks to optimize water delivery. Experiment showed a 50% reduction in water use and irrigation time.
- The paper presents a LoRaWAN based smart irrigation system deployed in a 22 ha olive grove in Greece. IoT nodes with soil moisture sensors at 30, 60 and 90 cm transmit long range data via a single gateway to a cloud system for real time monitoring and analysis. Operating for two years, system reduces water consumption by 42% in 2020 and 25% in 2021.
- The paper made a smart irrigation management system integrating embedded systems, IoT, sensors, telemetry, and cloud computing to optimize water use in agriculture. Field tests showed efficient monitoring of temperature, humidity, moisture and water levels.
- This study makes a smart agriculture system integrating IoT sensors, predictive algorithms, and automated irrigation control. Field trials achieved a 30% reduction in water use while maintaining optimal moisture, lower labour and energy costs.
- The paper presents an IoT based intelligent system integrating embedded hardware, fuzzy logic and cloud computing to improve water use. Fuzzy logic dynamically adjusts irrigation based on environmental conditions, maintaining soil moisture near a 62% target and significantly reducing water waste.
- The paper analyses the impact of Climate Smart Agriculture (CSA) adoption on food security and income of households across Zimbabwe. The findings indicate that the adoption of CSA has a positive impact on the welfare of farmers.
- This study mapped precision agriculture in sub-Saharan Africa, narrowing 7715 publications to 128 relevant studies. Most research occurred in technologically advanced countries such as South Africa, Nigeria and Kenya. With 21 countries lacking research and minimal focus on livestock, substantial opportunities remain for expanding precision agriculture across the region.
- This study reviews current developments, drivers, barriers and policies supporting sustainable precision agriculture and future smart greenhouse adoption in Qatar.
- This study evaluated climate-smart agricultural practices to improve energy and economic efficiency in India's rice-wheat system. Using a three year on farm trial, practices including reduced tillage, residue retention, precision nutrient and irrigation management significantly increased net energy and efficiency by upto 51% and boosted income 18% compared to conventional tillage.

- This paper presents a machine learning based crop selection system combining weather and soil parameters to recommend optimal crops. Weather is predicted using LSTM-RNN, achieving low RMSE values, while crop selection uses a Random Forest classifier with 97.2% accuracy.
- The study compared two precision irrigation DSS, SETMI and ISSCADA, on a 58 hectare maize-soyabean field using variable rate irrigation. Both systems reduced irrigation without sacrificing yield.
- The six year study in Israel evaluated irrigation strategies for intensively cultivated jojoba. Treatments included control irrigation, 75% low irrigation, 125% high irrigation, and regulated deficit irrigation (RDI). More water increased vegetative growth and seed number but yield gains were smaller than water increases. RDI maintained yields comparable to control with 15% higher water productivity but reduced mechanical harvest efficiency.
- This study evaluated UAV based thermal remote sensing and evapotranspiration models to detect grapevine water stress for precision irrigation.
- This paper studies dynamic precision irrigation for cotton using variable rate application and weekly remote sensing based re zoning. Drone derived NDVI and thermal CWSI guided irrigation decisions compared to static management zones with uniform commercial irrigation. Dynamic zoning reduced spatial variability and increased water productivity by 19%
- This study optimized greenhouse irrigation using an IoT based monitoring system comparing SDI and SSDI at three water levels. SSDI produced lower vapor pressure deficits, cooler canopies, and higher yields (33.6 t/ha) at 80% CWR.

IV. CONCLUSION

Smart agriculture technologies have shown significant progress in revolutionizing traditional farming using digital intelligence, automation, and data centric methodologies. The review of forty recent studies demonstrates the effectiveness of IoT assisted monitoring, precision irrigation, UAV based environmental sensing, renewable energy integration, and AI powered decision support systems in improving crop yield, reducing water consumption, and enhancing sustainability. Field trials and real world deployments confirm substantial improvements, including water savings, increased energy efficiency, reduced labour requirements, and improved agricultural productivity.

Despite rapid developments, challenges such as system scalability, interoperability, maintenance complexity, cybersecurity risks, and high deployment cost remain barriers to widespread adoption, particularly in developing regions. Future research should focus on standardized communication

frameworks, low cost hardware, hybrid renewable energy solutions, explainable AI models, human-machine collaboration, and integration of localized agronomic knowledge.

Overall, smart agriculture presents a transformative opportunity to support global food security, climate resilience, and sustainable farming. Continued innovation and collaborative research between academia, industry, and government agencies will accelerate the transition toward Agriculture 5.0 and strengthen the foundation for intelligent, autonomous, and resource efficient farming ecosystems.

REFERENCES

1. Jaime Lloret, Sandra Sendra, Laura Garcia and Jose M. Jimenez "A Wireless Sensor Network Deployment for Soil Moisture Monitoring in Precision Agriculture" *Sensors* 2021, 21(21), 724.
2. Soham Adla, Neeraj Kumar Rai, Sri Harsha Karumanchi, Shivam Tripathi, Markus Disse and Saket Pande "Laboratory Calibration and Performance Evaluation of Low-Cost Capacitive and Very Low-Cost Resistive Soil Moisture Sensors" *Sensors* 2020, 20(2), 363.
3. Jehangir Arshad, Musharraf Aziz, Asma A. Al-Huqail, Muhammad Hussnain uz Zaman, Muhammad Husnain, Ateeq Ur Rehman and Muhammad Shafiq "Implementation of a LoRaWAN Based Smart Agriculture Decision Support System for Optimum Crop Yield" *Sustainability* 2022, 14(2), 827.
4. Chouaib El Hachimi, Salwa Belaqqiz, Saïd Khabba, Badreddine Sebbar, Driss Dhiba and Abdelghani Chehbouni "Smart Weather Data Management Based on Artificial Intelligence and Big Data Analytics for Precision Agriculture" *Agriculture* 2023, 13(1), 95.
5. Juan Contreras-Castillo, Juan Antonio Guerrero-Ibañez, Pedro C. Santana-Mancilla and Luis Anido-Rifón "SAgriculture-IoT: An IoT-Based Platform and Deep Learning for Greenhouse Monitoring" *Appl. Sci.* 2023, 13(3), 1961.
6. Gilroy P. Pereira, Mohamed Z. Chaari and Fawwad Daroge "IoT-Enabled Smart Drip Irrigation System Using ESP32" *IoT* 2023, 4(3), 221-243.
7. Avay Risal; Haoyu Niu, Jose Luis Landivar-Scott, Murilo M. Maeda, Craig W. Bednarz, Juan Landivar-Bowles, Nick Duffield, Paxton Payton, Pankaj Pal, Robert J. Lascano, Timothy Goebel and Mahendra Bhandari "Improving Irrigation Management of Cotton with Small Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV) in Texas High Plains" *Water* 2024, 16(9), 1300.
8. Rabaie Benameur, Amine Dahane, Bouabdellah Kechar and Abou El Hassan Benyamina "An Innovative Smart and Sustainable Low-Cost Irrigation System for Anomaly Detection Using Deep Learning" *Sensors* 2024, 24(4), 1162.

9. Ying Zhang, Xingchen Wang, Liyong Jin, Jun Ni, Yan Zhu, Weixing Cao and Xiaoping Jiang “Research and Development of an IoT Smart Irrigation System for Farmland Based on LoRa and Edge Computing” *Agronomy* 2025, 15(2), 366.
10. Emmanuel Torres-Quezada, Fernando Fuentes-Peñailillo, Karen Gutter, Félix Rondón, Jorge Mancebo Marmolejos, Willy Maurer and Arturo Bisono “Remote Sensing and Soil Moisture Sensors for Irrigation Management in Avocado Orchards: A Practical Approach for Water Stress Assessment in Remote Agricultural Areas” *Remote Sens.* 2025, 17(4), 708.
11. Arvind Kumar, Abhijeet Kumar, Abhishek Kumar Singh and Anubhav Kumar Choudhary “IoT Based Energy Efficient Agriculture Field Monitoring and Smart Irrigation System using NodeMCU” *Journal of Mobile Multimedia* 17(1-3) January 2021, 345 – 360.
12. Hatem A. Alharbi and Mohammad Aldossary “Energy-Efficient Edge-Fog-Cloud Architecture for IoT-Based Smart Agriculture Environment” *IEEE Access* 9, 110480 - 110492, 30 July 2021.
13. Et-Taibi Bouali, Mohamed Riduan Abid, El-Mahjoub Boufounas, Tareq Abu Hamed and Driss Benhaddou “Renewable Energy Integration Into Cloud & IoT-Based Smart Agriculture” *IEEE Access* 10, 1175 – 1191, 23 December 2021.
14. Muhammad Shoaib Farooq, Shamyala Riaz, Mamoun Abu Helou, Falak Sher Khan, Adnan Abid and Atif Alv “Internet of Things in Greenhouse Agriculture: A Survey on Enabling Technologies, Applications, and Protocols” *IEEE Access* 10, 53374 – 53397, 11 April 2022.
15. Amel Dechemi, Dimitrios Chatziparaschis, Joshua Chen, Merrick Campbell, Azin Shamshirgaran and Caio Mucchiani “Robotic Assessment of a Crop’s Need for Watering: Automating a Time-Consuming Task to Support Sustainable Agriculture” *IEEE Robotics & Automation Magazine* 30(4), 52 – 67, 26 October 2023.
16. Harikrishnan Muraleedharan Jalajamony, Midhun Nair, Patricia F. Mead and Renny Edwin Fernandez “Drone Aided Thermal Mapping for Selective Irrigation of Localized Dry Spots” *IEEE Access* 11, 7320 - 7335, 16 January 2023.
17. Andreas Holzinger and Iztok Fister and Iztok Fister and Hans-Peter Kaul and Senthold Asseng “Human-Centered AI in Smart Farming: Toward Agriculture 5.0” *IEEE Access* 12, 62199 - 62214, 30 April 2024.
18. Rubina Rashid, Waqar Aslam, Romana Aziz and Ghadah Aldehim “An Early and Smart Detection of Corn Plant Leaf Diseases Using IoT and Deep Learning Multi-Models” *IEEE Access* 12, 23149 - 23162, 22 January 2024.
19. Monica Dutta; Deepali Gupta, Sumegh Tharewal, Deepam Goyal, Jasminder Kaur Sandhu and Manjit Kaur “Internet of Things-Based Smart Precision Farming in Soilless Agriculture: Opportunities and Challenges for Global Food Security” *IEEE Access* 13, 34238 - 34268, 10 February 2025.
20. Baraa H. Jawad, Ola A. Alwesabi, Nibras Abdullah and Ahmed Abed Mohammed “Hybrid Artificial Neural Network Activation Function to Reduce Water Wastage in Agricultural Irrigation” *IEEE Access* 13, 93302 - 93322, 27 May 2025.
21. Ali Al-Naji, Ahmed Bashar Fakhri, Sadik Kamel Gharghan and Javaan Chahl “Soil color analysis based on a RGB camera and an artificial neural network towards smart irrigation: A pilot study” *Heliyon* Volume 7, Issue 1, January 2021, e06078.
22. P. Suresh, R. H. Aswathy, Sridevi Arumugam, Amani Abdulrahman Albraikan, Fahd N. Al-Wesabi, Anwer Mustafa Hilal and Mohammad Alamgeer “IoT with Evolutionary Algorithm Based Deep Learning for Smart Irrigation System” *Computers, Materials & Continua* 2022, 71(1), 1713-1728.
23. Yahia Serbouh, Taha Benikhelef, Djamel Benazzouz, Mohamed Abdessamed Ait Chikh, Sami Touil, Amina Richa and Hacene Mahmoudi “Performance optimization and reliability of solar pumping system designed for smart agriculture irrigation” *Desalination and Water Treatment* Volume 255, April 2022, Pages 4-12.
24. Shaleeza Sohail, Farnaz Farid, Sayka Jahan, Farhad Ahamed and Steven Gordon “An Interpretable Artificial Intelligence Based Smart Agriculture System Fariza Sabrina” *Computers, Materials and Continua* Volume 72, Issue 2, 26 March 2022, Pages 3777-3797.
25. Kit Joshua Wanyama, Paul Soddo, Prossie Nakawuka, Peter Tumutegyereize, Erion Bwambale, Isaac Oluk, William Mutumba and Allan John Komakech “Development of a solar powered smart irrigation control system” *Smart Agricultural Technology* Volume 5, October 2023, 100273.
26. Ehsan Pazouki “A smart surface irrigation design based on the topographical and geometrical shape characteristics of the land” *Agricultural Water Management* Volume 275, 1 January 2023, 108046.
27. Aglaia Liopa-Tsakalidi, Vasileios Thomopoulos, Pantelis Barouchas, Achilles D. Boursianis and Sotirios K. Goudos “A LoRaWAN-based IoT platform for smart irrigation in olive groves” *Smart Agricultural Technology* Volume 9, December 2024, 100673.
28. Abdennabi Morchid, Rachid Jebabra, Haris M. Khalid, Rachid El Alami, Hassan Qjidaa and Mohammed Ouazzani Jamil “IoT-based smart irrigation management system to enhance agricultural water security using embedded systems, telemetry data, and cloud computing” *Results in Engineering* Volume 23, September 2024, 102829.
29. Subir Gupta, Subrata Chowdhury, Ramya Govindaraj, Kassian T.T. Amesho, Sumarlin Shangdiar, Timoteus Kadhila and Sioni Iikela “Smart agriculture using IoT for automated irrigation, water and energy efficiency” *Smart*

- Agricultural Technology Volume 12, December 2025, 101081.
30. Abdennabi Morchid, Zafar Said, Almoataz Y. Abdelaziz, Pierluigi Siano and Hassan Qjidaa “Fuzzy logic-based IoT system for optimizing irrigation with cloud computing: Enhancing water sustainability in smart agriculture” Smart Agricultural Technology Volume 11, August 2025, 100979.
31. Angeline Mujeyi, Maxwell Mudhara & Munyaradzi Mutenje “The impact of climate smart agriculture on household welfare in smallholder integrated crop–livestock farming systems: evidence from Zimbabwe” Agriculture & Food Security Volume 10, article number 4, (2021).
32. Justine M. Nyaga, Cecilia M. Onyango, Johanna Wetterlind & Mats Söderström “Precision agriculture research in sub-Saharan Africa countries: a systematic map” Precision Agriculture Volume 22, pages 1217–1236, (2021).
33. Theodora Karanisa, Yasmine Achour, Ahmed Ouammi & Sami Sayadi “Smart greenhouses as the path towards precision agriculture in the food-energy and water nexus: case study of Qatar” Environment Systems and Decisions Volume 42, pages 521–546, (2022).
34. S. K. Kakraliya, H. S. Jat, Ishwar Singh, M. K. Gora, Manish Kakraliya, Deepak Bijarniya, P. C. Sharma & M. L. Jat “Energy and economic efficiency of climate-smart agriculture practices in a rice–wheat cropping system of India” Scientific Reports Volume 12, article number 8731, (2022).
35. Sita Rani, Amit Kumar Mishra, Aman Kataria, Saurav Mallik & Hong Qin “Machine learning-based optimal crop selection system in smart agriculture” Scientific Reports Volume 13, article number 15997, (2023).
36. Sandeep Bhatti, Derek M. Heeren, Susan A. O’Shaughnessy, Christopher M. U. Neale, Jacob LaRue, Steve Melvin, Eric Wilkening & Geng Bai “Toward automated irrigation management with integrated crop water stress index and spatial soil water balance” Precision Agriculture Volume 24, pages 2223–2247, (2023).
37. Alon Ben-Gal, Shamir Badichi, Yonatan Ron, Aviad Perry, Uri Yermiyahu, Zipora Tietel, Noemi Tel Zur & Arnon Dag “Effects of irrigation amounts and a deficit irrigation strategy on water status and yields of intensively cultivated jojoba (*Simmondsia chinensis*)” Irrigation Science Volume 42, pages 891–905, (2024).
38. V. Burchard-Levine, I. Borra-Serrano, J. M. Peña, W. P. Kustas, J. G. Guerra, J. Dorado, G. Mesías-Ruiz, M. Herrezuelo, B. Mary, L. M. McKee, A. I. de Castro, S. Sanchez-Élez & H. Nieto “Evaluating the precise grapevine water stress detection using unmanned aerial vehicles and evapotranspiration-based metrics” Irrigation Science Volume 43, pages 65–85, (2025).
39. A. Ben-Gal, A. Barski, O. Bukris, H. Yasuor, S. A. O’Shaughnessy, N. C. Hansen, A. Peeters & Y. Cohen “Dynamic approaches to precision irrigation of cotton” Precision Agriculture Volume 26, article number 64, (2025).
40. Abdelrahman A. El-Sheshny, Amal M. Abdel-Hameed, M. A. Al-Rajhi, Hamed G. Ghanem, Taha M. Elzanaty & Mostafa H. Fayed “Optimizing water management in greenhouse farming through an IoT-enabled monitoring system” Journal of the Saudi Society of Agricultural Sciences Volume 24, article number 33, (2025).